

Effect of Technology Tasked-based Approach on Academic Performance in Listening Comprehension among Secondary School Students in Bwari, Abuja

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Abstract

This study titled: 'Effect of Technological Enhanced Tasked-based Approach on Academic Performance in Listening Comprehension among Secondary School Students in Bwari, Abuja', adopted a quasi-experimental research design. Three research objectives, questions and hypotheses were developed for the study. The population comprised of all the nine thousand five hundred and sixty-six (9,566) male and female Senior Secondary School 2 students during the 2021/2022 academic session in public Senior Secondary Schools in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. One hundred and seventeen (117) students were sampled randomly for the study using an intact class. The study adopted Structured Listening Comprehension Test (SLCT) as its instrument for data collection. The instrument was piloted using split-half test method. The scores of the reliability test were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC), and the instrument has a reliability index of 0.80. The simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach (TETBA) is significant on students' performance in listening comprehension compared to those exposed to lecture teaching method. The study concluded that Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach is effective in the teaching of listening comprehension. Based on this finding, the study recommended that teachers should use TETBA in teaching skills in listening comprehension at Secondary School level.

Keywords: Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach, Listening Comprehension, Academic Performance and Students

Introduction

The advent of modern technology in human society cannot be ignored; as it has impacted in all spheres of human life and environment. Its impacts over the years have provided solutions to societal problems as well as meeting immediate and future needs of man and his environment. Thus, technology is the application of scientific knowledge, tools and materials in meeting human and environmental needs. It refers to materials, tools, machine developed from the application of scientific knowledge. It extends to computers such as laptops, mobile phones, tablets, cameras, smart TV, smart board, projectors used in meeting educational needs of man (Kuijt, 2022). According to Salomon (2022), technology is the application of knowledge for meeting practical goals in a reproducible way. Oscar (2023) submits that technology is the application of scientific knowledge, skills and competences in filling the gaps traditional tools are unable to provide.

In education for example, the clamor for the use of technology cannot be over emphasized, as most educational institutions have switched from the use of traditional materials or tools to modern technology to ensure that the goals of teaching and learning are meant and the skills needed in learners are adequately developed. This is why the National Policy on Education 2013 states that educational activities should be learner-centered and practical; and that information technology should be used in teaching and learning. Therefore, it is expected that the teaching and learning process should be driven by modern technology for the actualization of these goals in various areas of learning, especially listening comprehension which this study is set to assess (Angela, 2022).

Listening comprehension is the ability to listen to a spoken or oral text, understand it and make meaning from it. It also means a listener's ability to separate between and among sounds or oral text. According to Brown & Yule as cited in Godwin (2021), listening comprehension means that a person understands what he/she has heard and makes meaning from it. Thus, when one listens to an audio text or lectures, or teaching, and makes meaning from it, he or she is said to be competent

in listening comprehension skills. It also refers to the various processes of understanding and making sense of spoken language. These involve knowing speech sounds, comprehending the meaning of individual words, and understanding the syntax of sentences. According to Anthony (2020), it is the understanding of sounds in utterances without the aid of any visual representation or medium. Thus, it is listeners' ability to identify main ideas, supporting details, as well as understand the literal, inferential and critical meaning of a text.

Listening comprehension is understood through its levels. These levels according to Williams as cited in Odumuh (2020) include: the literal, inferential, and the critical/evaluative level. The literal comprehension is an important level of understanding because it provides the foundation for more advanced comprehension. It involves identifying the important and essential information in the text. With guidance, students can distinguish between the important and less important ideas. This also means listening attentively to basic information in the text. The literal comprehension asks questions such as what, who, how, when, where, which, etc. The inferential comprehension determines what the text means. Determining inferential meaning requires listeners to think about the text and draw a conclusion. The focus shifts from basic information to listening to what the speaker says, paying close attention to the context of the text, and what it implies. Guiding students to recognize these perceived relationships, promotes understanding and decreases the risk of being overwhelmed by the complexities of the text being heard. Finally, the critical comprehension is the advanced form and involves analyzing or synthesizing information and applying it to other information in the text. Understandings at the literal and inferential or interpretive levels are combined, reorganized and restructured at the critical level to express opinions, draw new insights, develop fresh ideas, and conclusion. The critical level of listening comprehension helps the listeners to be a good thinker and critique, and by extension, have a clearer understanding about the text. Essentially, this level enables the listeners to closely interact with the authors' ideas and submissions in the text (Odumuh, 2020). Thus for effective undertaking of oral texts, these skills should be effectively taught to students.

However, studies have shown that the teaching of listening comprehension over the years has not been effective in developing its skills for better approach of an oral text; as many language teachers still use some of the earliest approaches, methods and materials. For example, the use of the Grammar Translation Method, Audio-lingual, etc. by many teachers in second language classroom is a setback to developing listening comprehension skills in learners, especially in their control of the listening skill and other aspects of English language that test learners' listening ability such as oral sound, and listening comprehension in particular (Odumuh, 2020).

Consequently, while researches have shown the positive impact of the use of technology in the teaching and learning of any skill in English language, the researcher notes that students' academic performance in English language, especially in listening skills and comprehension has not been encouraging. To justify the above, reports from national and international examinations bodies have shown the poor performance of students in English language, particularly listening skill and comprehension (Wisdom, 2022). In these examinations, the researcher observes that students find it difficult to discriminate between and among vowel and consonant sounds. For example, the difference between the short '/i/' and long '/i:/', '/o/' and '/u:/', '/e/' and '/æ/', '/tʃ/' and '/ʃ/', and '/s/' and '/z/', are often confusing to students learning listening skill. Another aspect of the listening comprehension that students often find difficult is identification of main idea and supporting details in paragraphs of an oral text, substituting words appropriately, and approaching literal, inferential and critical comprehension questions (Chen & Lin, 2018). The researcher observes that students find it challenging to perform all these tasks in a listening text, hence constitute a big challenge to performance. Thus, the need to incorporate in the second language classroom an approach and materials that will help make the teaching and learning of listening skills and comprehension in particular becomes the focus and desire of many language experts and researchers. In this case, the Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach is one language method that incorporates simulative technological tools and tasks in teaching and learning.

The Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach is one of the recent language methods that has dominated the teaching and learning of language. It is the use of technological devices such as smart board, projector, television, radio tape, speaker and microphones, ear phones, and other technological tools used in carrying out tasks or activities in the content of a subject. It also extends to mean the use of computer devices and internet in teaching and learning. Thus, the use of these devices and online learning platforms such as Telegram, WhatsApp, Microsoft Teams, among others in instilling knowledge and skills in learners are examples of the use of this approach. According to Chen & Lin (2018) and Xue (2020), the Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach makes the teaching and learning of listening comprehension interesting as well as reduces learners' anxiety to use language among themselves, in groups, and between their teachers. In the same vein, Pellerin's (2021) submits that mobile devices have positively contributed to task construction in encouraging learners in mastering language independently with meaningful and self-regulated language learning activities. According to him, these devices also help

learners to learn language from distance, as internet has given the opportunity for text of any kind to be sent to learners at any given time or place.

Furthermore, the Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach focuses on the use of authentic language to complete meaningful listening skill tasks in the target language. Such tasks may include conversing with a doctor, conducting an interview, or calling customer service for help. Assessment is primarily based on task outcome (the appropriate completion of real-world tasks) rather than on accuracy of prescribed language forms. For listening skill and comprehension, Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach helps enhance the listening comprehension competence in learners such as sound identification and recognition, phonemes separation, understanding oral communication or texts, as well as the overall interpretation of oral texts. This approach emphasizes how meaningful language learning activities with diverse real-life tasks can be used to impact listening comprehension skills in learners (Khoram & Zhang, 2023).

Adding to the submission of Khoram and Zhang (2023), Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach is relevant in listening comprehension classroom for the following reasons as identified by Martins (2021): Students easily connect their knowledge to tasks as activities in teaching make them active in the teaching and learning process, especially when technologies such as mobile smart phones, laptops, tablets, earphones, and other ICT materials are used; the use of tasks also creates contexts or situations that promote or facilitate listening skills, especially in the development of schemata; the context of listening to a text is better created when learners listen to a recorded text or message using radio or other ICT materials; tasks also gives learners the opportunity to be focused on the content of lesson, hence making teaching and learning effective; intrinsic motivation is easily created in learners when engaged with authentic listening skills and comprehension tasks; and this approach gives teachers the opportunity to observe what learners do and the areas they need to improve on. Other interesting tasks provided for effective teaching include: listen and draw scenes, adjectives draw, dramatization, speech presentation, sound discrimination, dialogues, announcement, to mention, a few.

Thus, Ellis (2020) proposes three stages for the use of this approach: Pre-task, main task, and post-task. The first stage is the pre-task phase. This phase is intended to actuate learners' prior linguistic knowledge of listening skill. Afterward, the task cycle phase is conducted by inviting learners to do some language activities in individual, pairs, groups to intensify their listening skill. During this phase, teachers serve as the learning facilitators. After completing the tasks cycles, the final pedagogical stage is orchestrated by reporting tasks, analyzing the language forms, and practicing similar tasks. In reporting tasks, particular learners should be ready to present their works (completed tasks). In so doing, the teaching and learning of listening skills becomes more effective as it is heavily driven by technology and tasks, which get them motivated and eager to learn. Taking into account the usefulness of Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach in the teaching and learning of listening comprehension, it becomes relevant that teachers of English language incorporate this language material and learning approach in the teaching and learning of listening comprehension.

Furthermore, there are lots of theories that have been proposed in understanding language learning. One of these theories is the schema theory. Schema theory is one of the cognitivist theories propounded by Jean Piaget in 1923. It was later expanded into a theory by an educational psychologist, Richard C. Anderson. The starting assumption of this theory is that the act of comprehension involves one's knowledge of the world. According to this theory, knowledge is a network of mental frames or cognitive constructs called schema, (plural) schemata. Schemata organize knowledge stored in the long term memory. The theory refers to a mental framework humans use to represent, organize and remember information. Schema theory presents our personal simplified view over reality derived from experience and prior knowledge; they enable one to recall, modify behaviour, concentrate attention on key information, or try to predict most likely outcomes of events (Gwimi, 2016). The relevant of this theory to the present work cannot be over emphasized. This is because the theory emphasizes importance of general knowledge and concepts that will enable listeners to activate their past experiences and use it in approaching a current or new knowledge (listening text).

Thus, related and relevant studies on the use of Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach in the teaching of English language at large are evidence. First, Abdullah and Saieed (2014) carried out a study on The Effect of Video-Based Tasks in Listening Comprehension of Iranian Pre-intermediate EFL Learners. The study found that teaching listening on the basis of video-based tasks has a significant effect on learners' listening comprehension in realizing and understanding authentic language more effectively. Aidi (2017) conducted a study on The Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Senior Secondary Students' Reading Comprehension Achievement in Gwagwalada Area Council, Abuja. The study showed that computer assisted instruction can improve the way students engage in reading and approaching comprehension text. Gio, Syahrial, and Wisma (2019) also carried out a study on The Effect of Task-Based Learning (TBL) Approach on the Students' Listening Comprehension at the Tenth Grade of SMAN Kota Bengkulu. The result showed that there was a significant effect of using

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TBL approach on the students' achievement in listening comprehension Laila (2020) carried out a study on A task-based Program for Developing Listening Comprehension and Listening Self-efficacy among EFL General Diploma Students. The results proved positive effect of the program on EFL General Diploma students who need suitable listening tasks in order to develop their listening comprehension skills and listening self-efficacy. Similar to the study of Laila, Burcu and Hüseyin (2021) conducted a research on The Effect of Digital Materials on Listening Comprehension Levels of Second Grade Elementary Students. The study also found that students taught listening comprehension using digital materials perform better than students taught without the materials. This finding suggests that digital materials are effective in the teaching of listening comprehension schools. Also, Dodi, Testiana, Charanjit, and Entika (2021), Rika, Nurdin, and Baso (2022), and Marina, Natalia, Evgeny, Anastasia, Tatyana and Nina (2023) conducted various studies on the use of technologies and task-based approach on teaching listening comprehension. The studies showed that students exposed to the treatment of technologies and tasks outperformed students who were not exposed to them.

Therefore, the above reviews have shown the relevance and effects of technology and task-based approach on the teaching and learning of listening comprehension as well as students' academic performance. The studies reviewed in this part of this research also indicate the relevance of the application of language learning materials, such as ICT, on the smooth teaching and learning processes. This is what the present study is interested in, with the desire to find out if Technology Enhanced Task-based Approach is effective in the teaching and learning of listening comprehension, and its impacts on students' academic performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of Technological Enhanced Tasked-based Approach on Academic Performance in Listening Comprehension among Secondary School Students in Bwari, Abuja. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the mean performance scores of students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method.
2. Examine the mean performance scores of students taught words substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method.
3. Examine the mean performance scores of students taught listening comprehension using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method in the treatment of literal, inferential and critical level;

Research Questions

1. What are the mean performance scores of students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method?
2. What are the mean performance scores of students taught words substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method?
3. What are the mean performance scores of students taught listening comprehension using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method in the treatment of the literal, inferential and critical levels?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught word substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method.
3. There is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught using technological enhanced task-based approach and those taught using lecture method at the literal, inferential and critical levels.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design. The experimental group were taught listening comprehension using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach, while the control group were using lecture method. The population comprised of all the nine thousand five hundred and sixty-six (9,566) male and female Senior Secondary School 2 students during the 2021/2022 academic session in public Senior Secondary Schools in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. One hundred and seventeen (117) students were sampled randomly for the study using an intact class. The study adopted Structured Listening Comprehension Test (SLCT) as its instrument for data collection. The instrument was piloted using split-half test

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method. The scores of the reliability test were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC), and the instrument has a reliability index of 0.80. The simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Additionally, the instrument was administered to the students by the research assistants, who were trained to carry out the function.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the mean performance scores of students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean score of students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	S D	
Experimental	TETBA	54	5.94	2.04	17.59	3.69	11.65
Control	Classroom texts	63	5.46	2.18	10.67	2.29	5.21
Mean Difference			0.48		6.92		6.44

Table 1 reveals the mean scores of both experimental and control groups. While there is similar mean score for both groups in the pre-test, the post-test result showed that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.59 with standard deviation of 3.69, and the control group had a mean score of 10.67 with standard deviation of 2.29. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 11.65 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 5.21. The table therefore showed that the experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.44 on the students' performance in main idea and supporting details. This showed that students in the experimental group have performed better than students in the control group in main idea and supporting details in listening comprehension.

Research Question 2

What are the mean performance scores of students taught words substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method?

Table 2: The mean performance scores of students taught words substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	S D	
Experimental	TETBA	54	5.20	2.28	15.87	2.62	10.67
Control	Classroom texts	63	5.70	2.61	9.56	1.65	3.86
Mean Difference			0.50		6.31		6.81

Table 2 reveals the mean scores of both experimental and control groups which are insignificant. However, the post-test result showed that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 15.87 with standard deviation of 2.62, while the control group had a mean score of 9.56 with standard deviation of 1.65. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 10.67 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.86. The table showed that experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.31 on the students' performance in words substitution. Therefore, students in the experimental group have performed better than students in the control group.

Research Question 3

What are the mean performance scores of students taught literal, inferential and critical comprehension using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method?

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Table 3: The mean performance scores of students taught literal, inferential and critical comprehension using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	S D	
Experimental	TETBA	54	5.57	2.80	17.20	2.44	10.67
Control	Classroom texts	63	5.65	3.24	9.49	2.16	3.86
Mean Difference			0.08		7.71		7.79

Table 3 reveals the mean scores of both experimental and control groups which are insignificant. However, the post-test result shows that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.20 with standard deviation of 2.44, while the control group had a posttest mean score of 9.49 with standard deviation of 2.16. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 11.63 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.84. The table showed that experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 7.71 on the students' performance in literal, inferential and critical comprehension. This showed that students in the experimental group performed better than students in the control group.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method.

Table 1: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	TETBA	54	17.59	3.69	115	12.214	.000	Rejected
Control	Classroom texts	63	10.67	2.29				

Table 1 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught main idea and supporting details using TETBA and the control group taught without it in listening comprehension as $t = 12.214$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught main idea and supporting details using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method is rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught word substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method.

Table 2: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	TETBA	54	15.87	2.62	115	15.229	.000	Rejected
Control	Classroom texts	63	9.56	1.65				

Table 2 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught words substitution using TETBA and the control group taught without it in listening comprehension as $t = 15.229$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught word substitution using Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach and those taught using lecture method is rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught using technological enhanced task-based approach and those taught using lecture method at the literal, inferential and critical levels.

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Table 3: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	TETBA	54	17.20	2.44	115	16.170	.000	Rejected
Control	Classroom texts	63	9.49	2.16				

Table 3 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught literal, inferential and critical comprehension using TETBA and the control group taught without it in listening comprehension as $t = 16.170$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in listening comprehension performance scores between students taught using technological enhanced task-based approach and those taught using lecture method at the literal, inferential and critical levels was rejected for the alternate.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis of the data above, the study found that Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach is significant on students' performance in listening comprehension in Senior Secondary Schools. This is justifiable based on the mean scores realized in the test administered to students taught main idea and supporting details, words substitution, and literal, inferential and critical comprehension. The study of Abdullah and Saieed (2014) which revealed the significant of the use of video-based tasks in listening comprehension tallies with this finding. This implies that the use of video-based tasks approach as a technological material aids the teaching of listening comprehension. Also, the studies of Laila, Burcu and Hüseyin (2021) Dodi, Testiana, Charanjit, and Entika (2021), Rika, Nurdin, and Baso (2022), and Marina, Natalia, Evgeny, Anastasia, Tatyana and Nina (2023) agree with the finding of this study that technologies and task-based approach are effective in teaching listening comprehension to students. Thus, the use of TETBA should be enhanced in the teaching of listening comprehension.

Conclusion

The need to implement the use of TETBA in the teaching of listening comprehension cannot be ignore. Thus, the analysis of this study has shown its significance in stimulating learners as well as improving their performance in listening skills. The study concludes that TETBA is effective in teaching listening comprehension and improves students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made: Teachers of English language should always use the Technological Enhanced Task-based Approach in teaching all the skills in listening comprehension to learners. Also, government at all levels and school management should ensure that adequate technological tools are provided for the use of the TETBA in teaching listening comprehension to learners. School management should set-up a team to supervise and monitor the implementation level of the TETBA in teaching listening comprehension. Also, teachers of English language should be retrained occasionally for better understanding and effective implementation of this approach.

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